

**A STUDY OF SELF-ADAPTIVE INERTIAL ALGORITHM FOR SOLVING SPLIT
EQUILIBRIUM PROBLEM FOR A FINITE FAMILY OF NON-LINEAR
BI-FUNCTIONS IN REAL HILBERT SPACE**

SHAMSHAD HUSAIN¹, *UQBA RAFAT² and MOHD ASAD³

s.husain68@yahoo.com

uqba.1709@gmail.com

masad19932015@gmail.com

^{1,2,3} *Department of Applied Mathematics, Zakir Husain College of Engineering and
Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh 202002, India.*

Abstract: *The key objective of the present research is to study a self-adaptive inertial algorithm for solving a Split Equilibrium Problem(SEP) and Fixed Point Problem(FPP) for a finite family of non-linear bi-functions. Our result indicates that the sequence generated by the inertial algorithm converges strongly to a common solution of these problems under some precise conditions. Finally, we illustrate proposed algorithm and its convergence by a numerical example. Our result generalizes some important results in the literature.*

Keywords: **Non-expansive mappings, Split equilibrium problem, Fixed point problem, Self-adaptive method, Strong convergence.**

1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout this paper, unless otherwise stated, let \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 be two real Hilbert spaces with inner-product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ and induced norm $\| \cdot \|$. Let \mathcal{K}_i and Q_i for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ be the closed convex subsets of \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 respectively.

An equilibrium problem, which were introduced by Blum and Oetti[23] have intensively been studied and the span of idea and technique of equilibrium problem have a broad range of applications in the study of optimization problems, split feasibility problems and Nash equilibrium problem etc.

The equilibrium problem in a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} is to find $x^* \in \mathcal{K}$ such that

$$\Phi(x^*, y) \geq 0, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (1.1)$$

*uqba rafat (email: uqba.1709@gmail.com)

where \mathcal{K} is a non-void closed, convex subset of a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} and $\Phi : \mathcal{K} \times \mathcal{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a bi-function. The solution set of Equilibrium Problem is denoted by $EP(\Phi)$.

Split Equilibrium problem, which was introduced and studied by Kazmi and Rizvi[22] states that for $\mathcal{K}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{H}_1$ and $Q_1 \subseteq \mathcal{H}_2$, $\Phi : \mathcal{K}_1 \times \mathcal{K}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\Psi : Q_1 \times Q_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be non-linear bi-functions and $\mathcal{A} : \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_2$ be a bounded linear operator. Then SEP is to find $x^* \in \mathcal{K}_1$ such that

$$\Phi(x^*, x) \geq 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{K}_1. \tag{1.2}$$

and $y^* = \mathcal{A}x^* \in Q_1$ solves

$$\Psi(y^*, y) \geq 0, \quad \forall y \in Q_1$$

where \mathcal{K}_1 and Q_1 are closed convex subsets of \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 , respectively. The solution set of Split Equilibrium Problem is denoted by $SEP(\Phi, \Psi)$.

In this paper, we consider a Split Equilibrium Problem for a finite family of non-linear bi-functions. Let $\mathcal{K}_i \subseteq \mathcal{H}_1$ and $Q_i \subseteq \mathcal{H}_2$ be the closed convex subsets and $\Phi_i : \mathcal{K}_i \times \mathcal{K}_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\Psi_i : Q_i \times Q_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the non-linear bi-functions for every $i=1,2,3\dots n$ and the sense of 'i' for $i=1,2,3\dots n$, is same throughout the paper. Also, $\mathcal{A} : \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_2$ be a bounded linear operator. Then the problem is to find $x^* \in \mathcal{K}_i$ such that

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \Phi_i(x^*, x) \geq 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{K}_i$$

and $y^* = \mathcal{A}x^* \in Q_i$ solves

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \Psi_i(y^*, y) \geq 0, \quad \forall y \in Q_i$$

The solution set of Split equilibrium problem is denoted by $SEP[\Phi_i, \Psi_i]$.

Now, Consider a non-linear mapping $\mathcal{S} : \mathcal{K} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$. A point $x^* \in \mathcal{K}$ is called a fixed point of \mathcal{S} if $\mathcal{S}x^* = x^*$. We denote the set of all fixed points of \mathcal{S} by $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{S})$.

Suantai.et.al.[14] proposed the iterative scheme for finding a common solution of $SEP(\Phi, \Psi)$ and $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{S})$ for a non-spreading mappings in a Hilbert space:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &\in \mathcal{K} \\ u_n &= T_{r_n}^\Phi (I - \gamma A^* (I - T_{r_n}^\Psi) A) x_n \\ x_{n+1} &= \alpha_n x_n + (1 - \alpha_n) \mathcal{S} u_n, \end{aligned} \tag{1.3}$$

under some precise conditions we have proved that the sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges weakly to a common element of $SEP(\Phi, \Psi)$ and $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{S})$.

Neterov[12]introduced an algorithm which improves the rate of convergence of the sequence $\{x_n\}$ and called modified heavy ball method.

$$\begin{aligned} y_n &= x_n + \Theta_n(x_n - x_{n-1}) \\ x_{n+1} &= y_n - \lambda_n \Delta f(y_n) \end{aligned} \tag{1.4}$$

for each $n \geq 1$, $\lambda_n \geq 0$, $\Theta_n \in (0, 1)$ is an extrapolation factor, f is a convex function and Δf is the gradient f .

Very recently, Alakoya and Owolabi[21] introduced an inertial algorithm with self-adaptive step size for split equilibrium problem for an infinite family of strict pseudo-contractions. The algorithm proposed by them is given by

$$\begin{aligned} w_n &= x_n + \Theta_n(x_n - x_{n-1}). \\ z_n &= T_{r_n}^\Phi(w_n + \tau_n A^*(T_{r_n}^\Psi - I)Aw_n), \\ x_{n+1} &= \alpha_n \gamma f(x_n) + (I - \alpha_n \mathcal{D})[(1 - \beta_n)z_n + \beta_n \mathcal{W}_n z_n] \end{aligned} \tag{1.5}$$

The above sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly under some precise conditions on parameters.

Motivated and inspired by above results and algorithm, we introduce an inertial iterative scheme with self -adaptive step size for finding a common solution of Split equilibrium problem for a finite family of non-linear bi-functions and fixed point problem in a real Hilbert space. We also formed the strong convergence of the proposed method and presented a numerical example to demonstrate the potency of the algorithm.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Let symbols \rightarrow and \rightharpoonup denote strong and weak convergence, respectively. Let \mathcal{H} be a real Hilbert space and \mathcal{K} be any nonempty closed convex subset in \mathcal{H} , we define a metric projection $P_{\mathcal{K}} : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ as for each $x \in \mathcal{H}$ there is a unique element $P_{\mathcal{K}}x \in \mathcal{K}$ such that

$$\|x - P_{\mathcal{K}}x\| = \inf\{\|x - z\| : z \in \mathcal{K}\} \tag{2.1}$$

It is known that $P_{\mathcal{K}}$ is nonexpansive and has the following properties:

(i) for all $x, y \in \mathcal{K}$,

$$\|P_{\mathcal{K}}x - P_{\mathcal{K}}y\|^2 \leq \langle P_{\mathcal{K}}x - P_{\mathcal{K}}y, x - y \rangle,$$

(ii) for any $x \in \mathcal{H}$ and $z \in \mathcal{K}$, $z = P_{\mathcal{K}}x \iff \langle x - z, z - y \rangle \geq 0$ for all $y \in \mathcal{K}$,

(iii) for any $x \in \mathcal{H}$ and $y \in \mathcal{K}$,

$$\|P_{\mathcal{K}}x - y\|^2 + \|x - P_{\mathcal{K}}x\|^2 \leq \|x - y\|^2,$$

(iii) for any $x, y \in \mathcal{H}$ with $y \neq 0$, let $Q = \{z \in \mathcal{H} : \langle y, z - x \rangle \leq 0\}$ then, for all $u \in \mathcal{H}$, $P_Q(u)$ is given by

$$P_Q(u) = u - \max\left\{0, \frac{\langle y, u - x \rangle}{\|y\|^2}\right\}y,$$

which gives an explicit formula for computing the projection of any point onto a half-space.

Subsequently, we denote the weak convergence and strong convergence of a sequence $\{x_n\}$ to a point $x \in \mathcal{H}$ by $x_n \rightharpoonup x$ and $x_n \rightarrow x$ respectively and $w_w(x_n)$ denotes the set of weak limits of $\{x_n\}$ then

$$w_w(x_n) := \{x \in \mathcal{H} : x_{n_k} \rightharpoonup x \text{ for some subsequence } \{x_{n_k}\} \text{ of } \{x_n\}\}.$$

Now, we present some definitions and lemmas which employed in our subsequent studies.

Definition 2.1. A mapping $T : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ is called

(i) L-Lipschitzian or Lipschitz continuous on \mathcal{H} , if there exists $L > 0$ such that

$$\|Tx - Ty\| \leq L\|x - y\|, \forall x, y \in \mathcal{H}$$

if $L \in [0, 1)$, then T is called contraction mapping;

(ii) non-expansive if T is 1-Lipschitzian;

(iii) firmly non-expansive if $\mathcal{F}(T) \neq \emptyset$ and

$$\|Tx - Ty\|^2 \leq \langle T(x) - T(y), x - y \rangle, \forall x, y \in \mathcal{H}.$$

or equivalently

$$\|Tx - Ty\|^2 \leq \|x - y\|^2 - \|(I - T)x - (I - T)y\|^2, \forall x, y \in \mathcal{H};$$

(iv) quasi-non-expansive if $\mathcal{F}(T) \neq \emptyset$ and

$$\|Tx - p\| \leq \|x - p\|, \forall x \in \mathcal{H}, p \in \mathcal{F}(T).$$

(v) k-demicontractive if there exists a constant $k \in [0, 1)$ such that

$$\|Tx - p\|^2 \leq \|x - p\|^2 + k\|x - Tx\|^2, \forall x \in \mathcal{H}, p \in \mathcal{F}(T).$$

Definition 2.2. A mapping $T : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ is called

(i) monotone if

$$\langle Tx - Ty, x - y \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall x, y \in \mathcal{H};$$

(ii) α - strongly monotone, if there exists a constant $\alpha > 0$ such that

$$\langle Tx - Ty, x - y \rangle \geq \alpha \|x - y\|^2 \quad \forall x, y \in \mathcal{H};$$

(iii) β - inverse strongly monotone, if there exist a constant $\beta > 0$ such that

$$\langle Tx - Ty, x - y \rangle \geq \beta \|Tx - Ty\|^2 \quad \forall x, y \in \mathcal{H};$$

(iv) strongly positive if there exist a constant $\gamma > 0$ such that

$$\langle Tx, x \rangle \geq \gamma \|x\|^2, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H};$$

(v) averaged if there exist a non-expansive mapping $S : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ and a number $c \in (0,1)$, such that

$$T = (1 - c)I + cS.$$

Recall that the mapping $I - T$ is demiclosed at zero iff $x \in \mathcal{F}(T)$ whenever $x_n \rightarrow x$ and $(x_n - Tx_n) \rightarrow 0$. It is well known that if $T : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ is nonexpansive, then $I - T$ is demiclosed at zero.

Definition 2.3. Let $\{S_n\}$ be a sequence of k_n - strict pseudo-contractions. Define $S_n^i = t_n I + (1 - t_n)S_n$, $t_n \in (k_n, 1)$ then, \mathcal{W}_n is defined by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} Z_{n,n+1} = I, \\ Z_{n,n} = \xi_n S_n^i Z_{n,n+1} + (1 - \xi_n)I, \\ Z_{n,n-1} = \xi_n S_{n-1}^i Z_{n,n} + (1 - \xi_{n-1})I, \\ \dots, \\ Z_{n,k} = \xi_k S_k^i Z_{n,k+1} + (1 - \xi_k)I, \\ Z_{n,k-1} = \xi_{k-1} S_{k-1}^i Z_{n,k} + (1 - \xi_{k-1})I, \\ \dots, \\ Z_{n,2} = \xi_2 S_2^i Z_{n,3} + (1 - \xi_2)I, \\ \mathcal{W}_n = Z_{n,2} = \xi_1 S_1^i Z_{n,2} + (1 - \xi_1)I, \end{array} \right. \quad (2.2)$$

where $\{\xi_i\}$ is a sequence of real numbers such that $0 \leq \xi_i \leq 1$ for all $i \geq 1$. For each $n \geq 1$, such a mappings \mathcal{W}_n are non-expansive.

Assumption 2.1. Let $\Phi_i : \mathcal{K}_i \times \mathcal{K}_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the non-linear bi-functions satisfying the following conditions:

(i) $\Phi_i(x, x) \geq 0$, for all $x \in \mathcal{K}_i$, for $i=1,2,3,\dots,n$;

- (ii) Φ_i is monotone, i.e., $\Phi_i(x, y) + \Phi_i(y, x) \leq 0$, for all $x, y \in \mathcal{K}_i$;
- (iii) Φ_i is upper hemi-continuous, i.e., for each $x, y, z \in \mathcal{K}_i$,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \sup \Phi_i(tz + (1-t)x, y) \leq \Phi_i(x, y)$$
;
- (iv) for each fixed $x \in \mathcal{K}_i$, function $y \mapsto \Phi_i(x, y)$ is convex and lower semi-continuous;

let $\Psi_i : Q_i \times Q_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the non-linear bi-functions such that

- (a) $\Psi_i(x, x) \geq 0$, for all $x \in Q_i$;
- (b) for each fixed $y \in Q_i$, function $x \mapsto \Psi_i(x, y)$ is upper semi-continuous;
- (c) for each fixed $x \in Q_i$, function $y \mapsto \Psi_i(x, y)$ is convex and lower semi-continuous;

and assume that for fixed $r > 0$ and $z \in Q_i$, there exist a non-empty compact convex subset \mathcal{K} of \mathcal{H}_1 and $x \in Q_i \cap \mathcal{K}$ such that

$$\Phi_i(y, x) + \Psi_i(y, x) + \frac{1}{r} \langle y - x, x - z \rangle \leq 0, \text{ for all } y \in Q_i - \mathcal{K}$$

Lemma 2.1. Let \mathcal{H} be a real Hilbert space. Then the following results holds $\forall x, y \in \mathcal{H}$ and $\delta \in (0, 1)$:

- (i) $\|x + y\|^2 \leq \|x\|^2 + 2\langle y, x + y \rangle$;
- (ii) $\|x + y\|^2 = \|x\|^2 + 2\langle x, y \rangle + \|y\|^2$;
- (iii) $\|x - y\|^2 = \|x\|^2 - 2\langle x, y \rangle + \|y\|^2$;
- (iv) $\|\delta x + (1 - \delta)y\|^2 = \delta\|x\|^2 + (1 - \delta)\|y\|^2 - \delta(1 - \delta)\|x - y\|^2$.

Lemma 2.2. Assume that the bifunction $\Phi_i : \mathcal{K}_i \times \mathcal{K}_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfy the conditions of Assumption 2.1. For $r > 0$ and $\forall x \in \mathcal{H}_1$. Define a mapping $T_r^{\Phi_i} : \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_i$ as follows:

$$T_r^{\Phi_i}(x) = \left[z \in \mathcal{K}_i : \sum_{i=1}^n \Phi_i(z, y) + \frac{1}{r} \langle y - z, z - x \rangle, \forall y \in \mathcal{K}_i \right]$$

Then, the following holds good:

- (i) $T_r^{\Phi_i}$ is nonempty and single-valued.
- (ii) $T_r^{\Phi_i}$ is firmly nonexpansive, i.e.,

$$\|T_r^{\Phi_i}x - T_r^{\Phi_i}y\|^2 \leq \langle T_r^{\Phi_i}x - T_r^{\Phi_i}y, x - y \rangle, \text{ for all } x, y \in \mathcal{H}_1$$

Lemma 2.3. Let $\{a_n\}$ be a sequence of non-negative real number, $\{\alpha_n\}$ be sequence in $(0,1)$ with $\sum_{n=0} \alpha_n = \infty$ and $\{b_n\}$ be a sequence of real numbers. Assume that

$$a_{n+1} \leq (1 - \alpha_n)a_n + \alpha_n b_n, \forall n \geq 1,$$

if $\limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} b_{n_k} \leq 0$ for every subsequence $\{a_{n_k}\}$ of $\{a_n\}$ satisfying $\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} (a_{n_{k+1}} - a_{n_k}) \geq 0$ then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = 0$.

Lemma 2.4. Let \mathcal{H} be a Hilbert space satisfies the optimal condition i.e, for any sequence $\{x_n\}$ with $x_n \rightarrow x$, then the inequality $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x\| < \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - y\|$ holds $\forall y \in \mathcal{H}$ with $y \neq x$.

3. MAIN RESULT

This section deals with algorithm and its convergence. Let \mathcal{K}_i and Q_i be nonempty closed convex subset of real Hilbert spaces \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 , respectively.

Condition A:

(A₁): $\mathcal{A} : \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_2$ is a bounded linear operator and $\mathcal{A}^* : \mathcal{H}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_1$ is a conjugate transpose of \mathcal{A} ;

(A₂): $\Phi_i : \mathcal{K}_i \times \mathcal{K}_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\Psi_i : Q_i \times Q_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are bi-functions, where Φ_i are monotone mappings and Ψ_i are upper semi-continuous mappings although satisfying Assumption 2.1;

(A₃): $\mathcal{D} : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ is strongly positive, bounded linear operator with coefficient $\bar{\gamma}$;

(A₄): $f : \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_2$ is a contraction mapping with coefficient $\rho \in (0, 1)$ and $0 < \gamma < \frac{\bar{\gamma}}{\rho}$;

(A₅): Let us define the solution set of our problem is given by $\Sigma = SEP[(\Phi_i, \Psi_i)] \cap \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathcal{F}(S_i)$ is a non empty, where $S_i : \mathcal{K}_i \rightarrow \mathcal{K}_i$ is an infinite family of k_i -strict pseudo contractions. Also, the defined solution set Σ is closed and convex.

Condition B:

(B₁): Let $\{\alpha_n\} \subset (0, 1)$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n = 0$ and $\sum_{n=0} \alpha_n = \infty$, $\{\beta_n\} \subset (0, 1)$

(B₂): Let $\Theta > 0$, $\{\Theta_n\}$ be a positive sequence such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\delta_n}{\alpha_n} = 0$, and $0 < a \leq \tau_n \leq b < 1$;

(B₃): $\{r_n\} \subset (0, \infty)$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} r_n > 0$.

Now, the algorithm is presented as follows:

Algorithm (3.1)

Step 1. Select $x_0, x_1 \in \mathcal{K}_i$ be two arbitrary initial points and set $n = 1$

Step 1. Given $(n - 1)^{th}$ and n^{th} iterates, choose Θ_n such that $0 \leq \Theta_n \leq \hat{\Theta}_n$

$$\hat{\Theta}_n = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \min\{\Theta_n, \frac{\delta_n}{\|x_n - x_{n-1}\|}\} & \text{if } x_n \neq x_{n-1} \\ \Theta & \text{otherwise} \end{array} \right\} \tag{3.1}$$

Step 2. Set

$$w_n = x_n + \Theta_n(x_n - x_{n-1}) \tag{3.2}$$

Step 3. Compute

$$z_n = T_{r_n}^{\Phi_i}(w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n), \tag{3.3}$$

where

$$\gamma_n := \begin{cases} \tau_n \frac{\|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2}{\|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|} & \text{if } \mathcal{A}w_n \neq T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}\mathcal{A}w_n \\ \lambda & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{3.4}$$

Step 4. Compute

$$x_{n+1} = \alpha_n \gamma f(x_n) + (I - \alpha_n \mathcal{D})[(1 - \beta_n)z_n + \beta_n \mathcal{W}'_n z_n] \tag{3.5}$$

Set $n := n + 1$ and return to **step1**.

We noticed from the conditions (B_1) and (B_2) that,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Theta_n \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| = 0. \tag{3.6}$$

STEP(1): First, we show that the sequence $\{x_n\}$ is bounded.

Proof. Let $P_\Sigma(I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)$ is a projection map on the set Σ and $\forall x, y \in \mathcal{H}_1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_\Sigma(I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)(x) - P_\Sigma(I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)(y)\| &\leq \|(I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)(x) - (I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)(y)\| \\ &\leq \|(I - \mathcal{D})x - (I - \mathcal{D})y\| + \gamma \|fx - fy\| \\ &\leq (1 - \bar{\gamma})\|x - y\| + \gamma \rho \|x - y\| \\ &= (1 - (\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho))\|x - y\|. \end{aligned}$$

This shows that the projection map $P_\Sigma(I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)$ is a contraction. Hence, there exist an element $p \in \Sigma$ such that $p = P_\Sigma(I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)(p)$.

Let $p \in \Sigma$, then we have that $Sp = p$, $T_{r_n}^{\Phi_i}(p) = p$ and $T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}(\mathcal{A}p) = \mathcal{A}p$, since $T_{r_n}^{\Phi_i}$ are non-expansive mappings, then we obtain from Lemma (2.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \|z_n - p\|^2 &= \|T_{r_n}^{\Phi_i}(w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n) - p\|^2 \\ &= \|T_{r_n}^{\Phi_i}(w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n) - T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}p\|^2 \\ &\leq \|(w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n) - p\|^2 \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

$$= \|w_n - p\|^2 + \gamma_n^2 \|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2 + 2\gamma_n \langle w_n - p, \mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n \rangle \quad (3.8)$$

Again, by Lemma (2.1) and using the nonexpansivity of $T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle w_n - p, \mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n \rangle \\ &= \langle \mathcal{A}(w_n - p), (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n \rangle \\ &= \langle T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p - (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n, (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n \rangle \\ &= \langle T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p - (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n \rangle - \langle (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n, (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n \rangle \\ &= \langle T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p - (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n \rangle - \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} [\|T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p\|^2 + \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2 - \|T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p - (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2] \\ &\quad - \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} [\|T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p\|^2 - \|\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p\|^2 - \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2] \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} [\|\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p\|^2 - \|\mathcal{A}w_n - \mathcal{A}p\|^2 - \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2] \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

Substituting (3.9) into (3.8) and by the definition of γ_n and the condition of τ_n , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|z_n - p\|^2 &\leq \|w_n - p\|^2 + \gamma_n^2 \|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2 - \gamma_n \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2 \\ &= \|w_n - p\|^2 - \gamma_n(1 - \tau_n) \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

$$\leq \|w_n - p\|^2. \quad (3.11)$$

Next, by applying the triangle inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|w_n - p\| &= \|x_n + \Theta_n(x_n - x_{n-1}) - p\| \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\| + \Theta_n \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

Since, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| = 0$, it follows that there exist a constant $M_1 > 0$ such that $\frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| \leq M_1, \forall n \geq 1$. Hence, we have from inequality (3.12),

$$\|w_n - p\| \leq \|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n M_1 \quad (3.13)$$

Define $Z_n := (1 - \beta_n)I + \beta_n \mathcal{W}'_n$ for each $n \geq 1$ and conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \|Z_n z_n - p\| &= \|(1 - \beta_n)z_n + \beta_n \mathcal{W}'_n z_n - p\| \\ &= \|(1 - \beta_n)(z_n - p) + \beta_n(\mathcal{W}'_n z_n - p)\| \\ &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|z_n - p\| + \beta_n\|\mathcal{W}'_n z_n - p\| \\ &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|z_n - p\| + \beta_n\|z_n - p\| \\ &= \|z_n - p\|. \end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

Hence, by using (3.11), (3.13) and (3.14), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_{n+1} - p\| &= \|\alpha_n \gamma f(x_n) + (1 - \alpha_n \mathcal{D})Z_n z_n - p\| \\ &= \|\alpha_n(\gamma f(x_n) - \mathcal{D}p) + (1 - \alpha_n \mathcal{D})(Z_n z_n - p)\| \\ &\leq \alpha_n\|(\gamma f(x_n) - \mathcal{D}p)\| + (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})\|(Z_n z_n - p)\| \\ &\leq \alpha_n\|(\gamma(f(x_n) - f(p)) + (\gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p))\| + (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})\|(z_n - p)\| \\ &= (1 - \alpha_n(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho))\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|\gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p\| + (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})\alpha_n M_1 \\ &= (1 - \alpha_n(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho))\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho) \left[\frac{\|\gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p\|}{\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho} + \frac{(1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})}{\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho} M_1 \right] \\ &\leq (1 - \alpha_n(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho))\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho)M^*. \end{aligned}$$

where, $M^* := \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \left[\frac{\|\gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p\|}{\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho} + \frac{(1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})}{\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho} M_1 \right]$. Setting $\alpha_n := \|x_n - p\|$, $b_n := \alpha_n(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho)M^*$, $c_n := 0$ and $\sigma_n := (\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho)$.

By Lemma (2.3) and using the conditions on the parameter it follows that $\{x_n\}$ is bounded. Consequently, $\{w_n\}$ and $\{z_n\}$ are also bounded.

STEP(2): For $p \in \Sigma$, we use Cauchy-Schwartz inequality and Lemma(2.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|w_n - p\|^2 &= \|x_n + \Theta_n(x_n - x_{n-1}) - p\|^2 \\ &= \|x_n - p\|^2 + \Theta_n^2\|x_n - x_{n-1}\|^2 + 2\Theta_n\langle x_n - p, x_n - x_{n-1} \rangle \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 + \Theta_n^2\|x_n - x_{n-1}\|^2 + 2\Theta_n\|x_n - x_{n-1}\|\|x_n - p\| \\ &= \|x_n - p\|^2 + \Theta_n\|x_n - x_{n-1}\|(\Theta_n\|x_n - x_{n-1}\| + 2\|x_n - p\|) \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 + 3M_2\Theta_n\|x_n - x_{n-1}\| \\ &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 + 3M_2\alpha_n \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n}\|x_n - x_{n-1}\|, \end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

where, $M_2 := \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \{\|x_n - p\|, \Theta_n \|x_n - x_{n-1}\|\} > 0$.

Next, by applying Lemma(2.1) and using(3.11) and (3.25), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|Z_n z_n - p\|^2 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)z_n + \beta_n \mathcal{W}_n z_n - p\|^2 \\
 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)(z_n - p) + \beta_n(\mathcal{W}_n z_n - p)\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|z_n - p\|^2 + \beta_n\|\mathcal{W}_n z_n - p\|^2 - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|\mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|z_n - p\|^2 + \beta_n\|z_n - p\|^2 - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|\mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n\|^2 \\
 &= \|z_n - p\|^2 - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|\mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n\|^2 \\
 &\leq \|x_n - p\|^2 + 3M_2 \alpha_n \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| - \gamma_n(1 - \tau_n) \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)A \mathcal{W}_n\|^2 \\
 &\quad - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|\mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n\|^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

Applying Lemma (2.1) and using (3.16), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_{n+1} - p\|^2 &= \|\alpha_n \gamma f(x_n) + (1 - \alpha_n \mathcal{D})Z_n z_n - p\|^2 \\
 &= \|\alpha_n(\gamma f(x_n) - \mathcal{D}p) + (1 - \alpha_n \mathcal{D})(Z_n z_n - p)\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \|Z_n z_n - p\|^2 + 2\alpha_n \langle \gamma f(x_n) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \{ \|x_n - p\|^2 + 3M_2 \alpha_n \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| - \gamma_n(1 - \tau_n) \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)A \mathcal{W}_n\|^2 \\
 &\quad - \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|\mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n\|^2 \} + 2\alpha_n \gamma \langle f(x_n) - f(p), x_{n+1} - p \rangle \\
 &\quad + 2\alpha_n \langle \gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \|x_n - p\|^2 + 3M_2 (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \alpha_n \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| - (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \{ \gamma_n(1 - \tau_n) \| \\
 &\quad (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)A \mathcal{W}_n\|^2 + \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|\mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n\|^2 \} \\
 &\quad + \alpha_n \gamma \rho (\|x_n - p\|^2 + \|x_{n+1} - p\|^2) + 2\alpha_n \langle \gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle.
 \end{aligned}$$

This implies that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_{n+1} - p\|^2 &\leq \frac{(1 - 2\alpha_n \bar{\gamma} + (\alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 + \alpha_n \gamma \rho)}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma_n \rho)} \|x_n - p\|^2 + 3M_2 \frac{(1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho)} \alpha_n \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| \\
 &\quad + \frac{2\alpha_n}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho)} \langle \gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle - \frac{(1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho)} \{ \gamma_n(1 - \tau_n) \|(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)A \mathcal{W}_n\|^2 \\
 &\quad + \beta_n(1 - \beta_n)\|\mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n\|^2 \} \\
 &= \frac{(1 - 2\alpha_n \bar{\gamma} + \alpha_n \gamma \rho)}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma_n \rho)} \|x_n - p\|^2 + \frac{(\alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma_n \rho)} \|x_n - p\|^2 \\
 &\quad + 3M_2 \frac{(1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho)} \alpha_n \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| + \frac{2\alpha_n}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho)} \langle \gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \frac{(1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho)} \{ \gamma_n (1 - \tau_n) \| (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \|^2 + \beta_n (1 - \beta_n) \| \mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n \|^2 \} \\
 & \leq \left(1 - \frac{2\alpha_n (\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho)}{1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho} \right) \| x_n - p \|^2 + \frac{2\alpha_n (\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho)}{(1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho)} \left[\frac{\alpha_n \bar{\gamma}^2 M}{2(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho)} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \frac{3M_2 (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \Theta_n}{2(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho) \alpha_n} \| x_n - x_{n-1} \| + \frac{1}{\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho} \langle \gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D} p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle \right] \\
 & - \frac{(1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2}{1 - \alpha_n \gamma \rho} \{ \gamma_n (1 - \tau_n) \| (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \|^2 + \beta_n (1 - \beta_n) \| \mathcal{W}_n z_n - z_n \|^2 \}
 \end{aligned}$$

where, $M := \sup \{ \| x_n - p \|^2 : n \in \mathbb{N} \}$.

STEP(3): For $p \in \Sigma$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have from (3.7) and (3.11).

$$\| w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n - p \|^2 \leq \| w_n - p \|^2$$

By applying Lemma (2.1) and the firmly non-exapansivity of $T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \| z_n - p \|^2 & = \| T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} (w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n) - p \|^2 \\
 & \leq \langle z_n - p, w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n - p \rangle \\
 & = \frac{1}{2} \{ \| z_n - p \|^2 + \| (w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n) - p \|^2 - \| (z_n - p) \\
 & \quad - (w_n + \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n) - p \|^2 \} \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} \{ \| z_n - p \|^2 + \| w_n - p \|^2 + \| z_n - w_n - \gamma_n \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \|^2 \} \\
 & = \frac{1}{2} \{ \| z_n - p \|^2 + \| w_n - p \|^2 - (\| z_n - w_n \|^2 + \gamma_n^2 \| \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \|^2 \\
 & \quad - 2\gamma_n \langle z_n - w_n, \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \rangle) \} \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} \{ \| z_n - p \|^2 + \| w_n - p \|^2 - (\| z_n - w_n \|^2 + \gamma_n^2 \| \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \|^2 \\
 & \quad + 2\gamma_n \| z_n - w_n \| \| \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \|) \} \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} \{ \| z_n - p \|^2 + \| w_n - p \|^2 - (\| z_n - w_n \|^2 + 2\gamma_n \| z_n - w_n \| \| \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \|) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

and this implies that

$$\| z_n - p \|^2 \leq \| w_n - p \|^2 - \| z_n - w_n \|^2 + 2\gamma_n \| z_n - w_n \| \| \mathcal{A}^* (T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I) \mathcal{A} w_n \| \tag{3.17}$$

Next, by applying Lemma (2.1) and using (3.14),(3.15) and (3.17), we have

$$\| x_{n+1} - p \|^2 = \| \alpha_n \gamma f(x_n) + (1 - \alpha_n \mathcal{D}) Z_n z_n - p \|^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \|\alpha_n(\gamma f(x_n) - \mathcal{D}p) + (1 - \alpha_n \mathcal{D})(Z_n z_n - p)\|^2 \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \|Z_n z_n - p\|^2 + 2\alpha_n \langle \gamma f(x_n) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \|z_n - p\|^2 + 2\alpha_n \langle \gamma f(x_n) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle \\
 &\leq (1 - \alpha_n \bar{\gamma})^2 \{ \|x_n - p\|^2 + 3M_2 \alpha_n \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| - \|z_n - w_n\|^2 \} \\
 &\quad + 2\gamma_n \|z_n - w_n\| \|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_n}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_n\| + 2\alpha_n \langle \gamma f(x_n) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n+1} - p \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

STEP(4): Next, we will show that for any subsequence $\{x_{n_k}\}$ of $\{x_n\}$ such that

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\|x_{n_{k+1}} - p\| - \|x_{n_k} - p\|) \geq 0$$

Then $x_{n_k} \rightharpoonup x^* \in \Sigma$ ie., $w_w \{x_n\} \subset \Sigma$, for any $p \in \Sigma$

from step(2), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{(1 - \alpha_{n_k} \bar{\gamma})^2}{(1 - \alpha_{n_k} \gamma \rho)} \beta_{n_k} (1 - \beta_{n_k}) \|W_{n_k} z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\|^2 &\leq \left(1 - \frac{2\alpha_{n_k} (\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho)}{1 - \alpha_{n_k} \gamma \rho}\right) \|x_{n_k} - p\|^2 - \|x_{n_{k+1}} - p\| \\
 &\quad + \frac{2\alpha_{n_k} (\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho)}{(1 - \alpha_{n_k} \gamma \rho)} \left[\frac{\alpha_{n_k} \bar{\gamma}^2 M}{2(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho)} \right. \\
 &\quad + \frac{3M_2 (1 - \alpha_{n_k} \bar{\gamma})^2 \Theta_{n_k}}{2(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho) \alpha_{n_k}} \|x_{n_k} - x_{n_{k-1}}\| \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\bar{\gamma} - \gamma \rho} \langle \gamma f(p) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n_{k+1}} - p \rangle \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

By the hypothesis of step(4) together with the fact that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_{n_k} = 0$, we get

$$\frac{(1 - \alpha_{n_k} \bar{\gamma})^2}{(1 - \alpha_{n_k} \gamma \rho)} \beta_{n_k} (1 - \beta_{n_k}) \|W_{n_k} z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\|^2 \rightarrow 0, k \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence, it follows that

$$\|W_{n_k} z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\|^2 \rightarrow 0, k \rightarrow \infty. \tag{3.18}$$

following similar argument, we obtain from step(2) that

$$\gamma_{n_k} (1 - \tau_{n_k}) \|(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\| \rightarrow 0, k \rightarrow \infty$$

By the definition of γ_n , which implies that

$$\frac{\|(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\|^2}{\|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\|} \rightarrow 0, k \rightarrow \infty$$

Since $\|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\|$ is bounded, then it follows that

$$\|(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\| \rightarrow 0, \quad k \rightarrow \infty \tag{3.19}$$

From this, we obtain

$$\|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\| \leq \|\mathcal{A}^*\| \|(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\| = \|\mathcal{A}\| \|(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\| \rightarrow 0, \quad k \rightarrow \infty \tag{3.20}$$

By applying (3.18), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|Z_{n_k}z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\| &= \|(1 - \beta_{n_k})z_{n_k} + \beta_{n_k}W_{n_k}z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\| \\ &= \|(1 - \beta_{n_k})(z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}) + \beta_{n_k}(W_{n_k}z_{n_k} - z_{n_k})\| \\ &\leq (1 - \beta_{n_k})\|z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\| + \beta_{n_k}\|W_{n_k}z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\| \rightarrow 0, \quad k \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \tag{3.21}$$

Also, from step(2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|z_{n_k} - w_{n_k}\|^2 &\leq (1 - \alpha_{n_k}\bar{\gamma})^2\|x_{n_k} - p\|^2 - \|x_{n_{k+1}} - p\| + (1 - \alpha_{n_k}\bar{\gamma})^2\{3M_2\alpha_{n_k}\frac{\Theta_{n_k}}{\alpha_{n_k}}\|x_{n_k} - x_{n_{k-1}}\| \\ &\quad + 2\gamma_{n_k}\|z_{n_k} - w_{n_k}\|\|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\|\} + 2\alpha_{n_k}\langle \gamma f(x_{n_k}) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n_{k+1}} - p \rangle \\ &\leq (1 - \alpha_{n_k}\bar{\gamma})^2\|x_{n_k} - p\|^2 - \|x_{n_{k+1}} - p\| + (1 - \alpha_{n_k}\bar{\gamma})^2\{3M_2\alpha_{n_k}\frac{\Theta_{n_k}}{\alpha_{n_k}}\|x_{n_k} - x_{n_{k-1}}\| \\ &\quad + 2M_3\|\mathcal{A}^*(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)\mathcal{A}w_{n_k}\|\} + 2\alpha_{n_k}\langle \gamma f(x_{n_k}) - \mathcal{D}p, x_{n_{k+1}} - p \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

where $M_3 := \sup\{\gamma_{n_k}\|z_{n_k} - w_{n_k}\| : k \in \mathbb{N}\}$.

By applying (3.20), using $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_{n_k} = 0$ together with the hypothesis of step(4) and using (3.6). We obtain

$$\|z_{n_k} - w_{n_k}\| \rightarrow 0, \quad k \rightarrow \infty \tag{3.22}$$

Again, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|w_{n_k} - x_{n_k}\| &= \|x_{n_k} + \Theta_{n_k}(x_{n_k} - x_{n_{k-1}}) - x_{n_k}\| \\ &\leq \|x_{n_k} - x_{n_k}\| + \Theta_{n_k}\|(x_{n_k} - x_{n_{k-1}})\| \rightarrow 0, \quad k \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \tag{3.23}$$

It follows from (3.18), (3.21), (3.22) and (3.23) that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{W}_{n_k}z_{n_k} - w_{n_k}\| = 0, \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{W}_{n_k}z_{n_k} - x_{n_k}\| = 0, \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|Z_{n_k}z_{n_k} - w_{n_k}\| = 0, \tag{3.24}$$

and

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|Z_{n_k} z_{n_k} - x_{n_k}\| = 0, \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|z_{n_k} z_{n_k} - x_{n_k}\| = 0. \quad (3.25)$$

By applying (3.25) and the fact that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_{n_k} = 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_{n_k+1} - x_{n_k}\| &= \|\alpha_{n_k} \gamma f(x_{n_k}) + (1 - \alpha_{n_k} \mathcal{D}) Z_{n_k} z_{n_k} - x_{n_k}\| \\ &= \alpha_{n_k} \|(\gamma f(x_{n_k}) - \mathcal{D} x_{n_k})\| + (1 - \alpha_{n_k} \bar{\gamma}) \|(Z_{n_k} z_{n_k} - x_{n_k})\| \rightarrow 0, \quad k \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned} \quad (3.26)$$

Now, we show that $w_w(x_n) \subset \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} F(S_i) = F(\mathcal{W})$. Let $x^* \in w_w(x_n)$ and suppose that $x^* \notin F(W)$ i.e, $\mathcal{W}x^* \neq x^*$. From (3.25), we have that $w_w(x_n) = w_w(z_n)$ and so, by Lemma (2.4),

$$\begin{aligned} \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|z_{n_k} - x^*\| &\leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|z_{n_k} - \mathcal{W}x^*\| \\ &\leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \{\|z_{n_k} - \mathcal{W}z_{n_k}\| + \|\mathcal{W}z_{n_k} - \mathcal{W}x^*\|\} \\ &\leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \{\|z_{n_k} - \mathcal{W}z_{n_k}\| + \|z_{n_k} - x^*\|\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.27)$$

Since $x_{n_k} \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall k \geq 1$ and $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\| = 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{W}z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\| &\leq \|\mathcal{W}z_{n_k} - \mathcal{W}_{n_k} z_{n_k}\| + \|\mathcal{W}_{n_k} z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\| \\ &\leq \sup_{k \in K} \|\mathcal{W}x - \mathcal{W}_{n_k} x\| + \|\mathcal{W}_{n_k} z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\|. \end{aligned}$$

An inequality (3.18) yeilds that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{W}z_{n_k} - z_{n_k}\| = 0$. Combining this with (3.27) gives

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|z_{n_k} - x^*\| < \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|z_{n_k} - x^*\|$$

which is a contradiction. Hence, we have $w_w(x_n) \subset F(\mathcal{W}) = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} F(S_i)$.

Now, we will prove that $w_w(x_n) \subset SEP[\Phi_i, \Psi_i]$

To acheive the aim first we show that $w_w(x_n) \subset EP(\Phi_i)$. Since $z_{n_k} = T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Phi_i}(w_{n_k} + \gamma_{n_k} A^*(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)Aw_{n_k})$, we have

$$\Phi_i(z_{n_k}, y) + \frac{1}{r_{n_k}} \langle y - z_{n_k}, z_{n_k} - w_{n_k} - \gamma_{n_k} A^*(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)Aw_{n_k} \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C,$$

which implies that

$$\Phi_i(z_{n_k}, y) + \frac{1}{r_{n_k}} \langle y - z_{n_k}, z_{n_k} - w_{n_k} \rangle - \frac{1}{r_{n_k}} \langle y - z_{n_k}, \gamma_{n_k} A^*(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I)Aw_{n_k} \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C,$$

$$\frac{1}{r_{n_k}} \langle y - z_{n_k}, z_{n_k} - w_{n_k} \rangle - \frac{1}{r_{n_k}} \langle y - z_{n_k}, \gamma_{n_k} A^* (T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} - I) A w_{n_k} \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C,$$

Since $z_{n_k} \rightharpoonup x^*$, then it follows from (3.12), (3.19), $\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} r_{n_k} > 0$, and condition (A₄) that

$$\Phi_i(y, x^*) \leq 0, \forall y \in C \tag{3.28}$$

Now, for $y \in \mathcal{K}_i$, let $y_t := ty + (1-t)x^* \quad \forall t \in (0, 1]$. This implies that $y_t \in \mathcal{K}_i$ and it follows from (3.28) that $\Phi_i(y, x^*) \leq 0$. So, by applying Assumption (A₁ – A₄), we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \Phi_i(y_t, y_t) \\ &\leq \Phi_i(y_t, y) + (1-t)\Phi_i(y_t, x^*) \\ &\leq t\Phi_i(y_t, y) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we have

$$\Phi_i(y_t, y) \geq 0, \forall y \in C. \tag{3.29}$$

letting $t \rightarrow 0$, by Condition (A₃), we have

$$\Phi_i(x^*, y) \geq 0, \forall y \in C. \tag{3.30}$$

this implies that $x^* \in EP(\Phi_i)$ Finally, we show that $Ax^* \in EP(\Psi_i)$. Since A is bounded linear operator and $w_w(x_n) = w_w(w_n)$ by (3.23), then we have $A_{n_k} \rightharpoonup Ax^*$. It then follows from that

$$T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} A w_{n_k} \rightharpoonup Ax^*, k \rightarrow \infty \tag{3.31}$$

By the definition of $T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} A w_{n_k}$, we have

$$\Psi_i(T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} A w_{n_k}, y) + \frac{1}{r_{n_k}} \langle y - T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} A w_{n_k}, T_{r_{n_k}}^{\Psi_i} A w_{n_k} - A w_{n_k} \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in Q_i$$

Since all Ψ_i are upper sem-continuous in the first argument, it follows from (3.23) and $\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} r_{n_k} > 0$ such that

$$\Psi_i(Ax^*, y) \geq 0, \forall y \in Q_i. \tag{3.32}$$

This shows that $Ax^* \in EP(\Psi_i)$. Hence, $w_w(x_n) \subset \Sigma$

STEP(5). Finally, we show that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x^*\| = 0$

For any $x^* \in \Sigma$, we have $x^* = P_\Sigma(I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)(x^*)$. Then it follows from step 3 that

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_{n+1} - x^*\|^2 &\leq \left(1 - \frac{2\alpha_n(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho)}{1 - \alpha_n\gamma\rho}\right) \|x_n - x^*\|^2 + \frac{2\alpha_n(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho)}{(1 - \alpha_n\gamma\rho)} \left[\frac{\alpha_n\bar{\gamma}^2 M}{2(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{3M_2(1 - \alpha_n\bar{\gamma})^2}{2(\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho)} \frac{\Theta_n}{\alpha_n} \|x_n - x_{n-1}\| + \frac{1}{\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\rho} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}(x^*), x_{n+1} - x^* \rangle \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3.33)$$

Now, we claim that the sequence $\{\|x_n - x^*\|\}$ converges to zero. In order to establish this, by Lemma (2.3), it suffices to show that $\limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}(x^*), x_{n_{k+1}} - x^* \rangle \leq 0$ for every subsequence $\{\|x_{n_k} - x^*\|\}$ of $\{\|x_n - x^*\|\}$ satisfying

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\|x_{n_{k+1}} - x^*\| - \|x_{n_k} - x^*\|) \geq 0.$$

Suppose that $\{\|x_{n_k} - x^*\|\}$ is a subsequence of $\{\|x_n - x^*\|\}$ such that

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\|x_{n_{k+1}} - x^*\| - \|x_{n_k} - x^*\|) \geq 0.$$

Then, by Step (4), we have that $w_w\{x_n\} \subset \Sigma$. It also follows from (3.25) that $w_w\{z_{n_k}\} = w_w\{x_n\}$. By the boundedness of $\{x_{n_k}\}$, there exist a subsequence $\{x_{n_{k_j}}\}$ of $\{x_{n_k}\}$ such that $x_{n_{k_j}} \rightharpoonup x$ and

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, x_{n_{k_j}} - x^* \rangle = \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, x_{n_k} - x^* \rangle = \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, z_{n_k} - x^* \rangle. \quad (3.34)$$

Since $x^* = P_\Sigma(I - \mathcal{D} + \gamma f)(x^*)$, it follows from (3.34) that

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, x_{n_{k_j}} - x^* \rangle = \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, x_{n_k} - x^* \rangle = \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, z_{n_k} - x^* \rangle \leq 0. \quad (3.35)$$

Hence, by (3.26) and (3.35), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, x_{n_{k+1}} - x^* \rangle &\leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, x_{n_{k+1}} - x_{n_k} \rangle + \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, x_{n_k} - x^* \rangle \\ &= \langle \gamma f(x^*) - \mathcal{D}x^*, x_{n_k} - x^* \rangle \leq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.36)$$

Applying Lemma (2.3) to (3.33) and using (3.32) together with the result in equation (3.6) and the condition on α_n , we end up with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x^*\| = 0$ as required.

This completes the proof. □

4. NUMERICAL DISCUSSION

In this section, we give a numerical example to illustrate the efficiency of the proposed algorithm.

Example.1: Let $\mathcal{H}_1 = \mathcal{H}_2 = \mathbb{R}$, $\mathcal{K}_i = \mathcal{Q}_i = \mathbb{R}$ with inner product defined by $\langle x, y \rangle = xy$ and let $\Phi_i : \mathcal{K}_i \times \mathcal{K}_i \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\Psi_i : \mathcal{Q}_i \times \mathcal{Q}_i \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the bi-functions, defined by

$$\Phi_i(x, y) = -5x^2 + xy + 4y^2$$

and

$$\Psi_i(x, y) = -9x^2 + xy + 8y^2$$

respectively and satisfied the conditions (A1) – (A5) after calculating.

we obtain

$$T_r^{\Phi_i}(u) = \frac{u}{9r+1}, \forall u \in \mathcal{K}_i$$

$$T_r^{\Psi_i}(v) = \frac{v}{17r+1}, \forall v \in \mathcal{Q}_i$$

Define a mapping $f : \mathbb{R} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $f(x) = \frac{x}{9}$ and let $\mathcal{A} : \mathbb{R} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by $\mathcal{A}(x) = \frac{x}{2}$ and $\mathcal{A}^*y = \frac{y}{2}$, where \mathcal{A} is a bounded linear operator $\forall x \in \mathbb{R}$.

Define an infinite family of $S_n : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$S_n x := -\frac{2}{n}x \tag{4.1}$$

Also, S_n is k_n -strictly pseudo contraction for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Define $S_n = t_n I + (I - t_n)$, $t_n \in [k_n, 1)$.

Let $f(x) = \frac{x}{5}$ and $\mathcal{D}(x) = \frac{x}{5}$ with constant $\bar{\gamma} = \frac{1}{7}$ which satisfies $0 < \gamma > \frac{\bar{\gamma}}{\rho}$. Choose $\tau_n = 0.6$, $\alpha_n = \frac{1}{n+5}$, $\delta_n = \frac{1}{(n+5)^2}$, $\beta_n = \frac{n+1}{2n+3}$, $r_n = \frac{n+2}{n+3}$, $t_n = \frac{1}{n+3}$. It can easily be checked that all the conditions on the control sequences in theorem (3) are satisfied.

Table 1: NUMERIC RESULT FOR EXAMPLE(1)

Number of iterations	$(x_0 = 1, x_1 = 1)$	$(x_0 = -1, x_1 = -1)$
1.	1.000000	-1.000000
2.	1.000000	-1.000000
3.	0.069143	-0.066451
4.	-0.043509	0.044411
5.	-0.006357	0.006232
6.	0.001392	0.001462
7.	0.000180	0.00175
8.	-0.000073	0.000075
9.	0.000004	0.000007
10.	0.000007	-0.000007
11.	-0.000000	0.000001
12.	-0.000001	0.000001
13.	0.000000	-0.00000

Table: For different intial values, we present a table for itrations above.

Figure 1: Shows the convergence for different intial values of x_0 and x_1

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper we had seen how the finite family of monotone operators and upper semi-continuous operators deals with the problem $SEP[\Phi_i, \Psi_i]$ by using the self adaptive algorithm with inertial proximal step. It would be interesting to focus on approximate solution of $SEP[\Phi_i, \Psi_i]$ and (FPP) as future research project. Further the approach of inertial self-adaptive method for the generalisation of equilibrium problem can be further exploited.

6. DECLARATION

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abass, H. A., Aremu, K. O., Jolaoso, L. O., and Mewomo, O. T. "An Inertial Forward-Backward Splitting Method For Approximating Solutions Of Certain Optimization Problems", *Nonlinear Funct. Anal.*(2020)
- [2] Kazmi, K. R., Khaliq, A., and Raouf, "An Iterative Approximation Of Solution Of Generalized Mixed Set-Valued Variational Inequality Problem". *MATHEMATICAL INEQUALITIES AND APPLICATIONS*, 10(3), 67 (2007).
- [3] Alakoya, T. O., Jolaoso, L. O., And Mewomo, O. T. "A Self Adaptive Inertial Algorithm For Solving Split Variational Inclusion And Fixed Point Problems With Applications", *Journal Of Industrial And Management Optimization* (2020).
- [4] Alakoya, T. O., Jolaoso, L. O. and Mewomo, O. T. "Two Modifications Of The Inertial Tseng Extragradient Method With Self-Adaptive Step Size For Solving Monotone Variational Inequality problems", *Demonstratio Mathematica*, 53(1), 208-224 (2021).
- [5] Bauschke, H. H. and Combettes, P. L. "A Weak-To-Strong Convergence Principle For Fejér-Monotone Methods In Hilbert Spaces", *Mathematics Of Operations Research*, 26(2), 248-264. (2001).
- [6] Censor, Y., Gibali, A., And Reich, "S.Algorithms For The Split Variational Inequality Problem. *Numerical Algorithms*", 59(2), 301-323. (2012).

- [7] Ceng, L. C., and Yao, J. C. “A Hybrid Iterative Scheme For Mixed Equilibrium Problems And Fixed Point Problems”, *Journal Of Computational And Applied Mathematics*, 214(1), 186-201. (2008).
- [8] Yao, Y., and Chen. “R.Strong Convergence Theorems For Strict Pseudo-Contractions In Hilbert Spaces”, *Journal Of Applied Mathematics And Computing*, 32(1), 69-82. (2010).
- [9] Dong, Q. L., Cho, Y. J., Zhong, L. L., and Rassias, T. M. “Inertial Projection And Contraction Algorithms For Variational Inequalities”, *Journal Of Global Optimization*, 70(3), 687-704. (2018).
- [10] Jolaoso, L. O., Alakoya, T. O., Taiwo, A., and Mewomo, O. T. “A Parallel Combination Extragradiant Method With Armijo Line Searching For Finding Common Solutions Of Infinite Families Of Equilibrium And Fixed Point Problems”, *Rendiconti Del Circolo Matematico Di Palermo Series 2*, 69(3), 711-735. (2020).
- [11] Jolaoso, L. O., Oyewole, O. K., Aremu, K. O., And Mewomo, O. T. “A new Efficient Algorithm For Finding Common Fixed Points Of Multivalued Demicontractive Mappings And Solutions Of Split Generalized Equilibrium Problems In Hilbert Spaces”, *International Journal Of Computer Mathematics*, 1-28. (2020).
- [12] Nesterov, Y. “A Method Of Solving a Convex Programming Problem With Convergence Rate $O(1/k^2)$ ” In *Sov. Math. Dokl (Vol. 27)*.
- [13] Shahzad, N., And Zegeye, H. “Approximating a Common Point Of Fixed Points Of a Pseudocontractive Mapping And Zeros Of Sum Of Monotone Mappings” ,*Fixed Point Theory and Applications*, 2014(1), 1-15. (2020).
- [14] Suantai, S., Cholamjiak, P., Cho, Y. J., and Cholamjiak, W. “On Solving Split Equilibrium Problems And Fixed Point Problems Of Nonspreading Multi-Valued Mappings In Hilbert Spaces”, *Fixed Point Theory And Applications*, 2016(1), 1-16. (2016).
- [15] Abass, H. A., Ogbuisi, F. U., And Mewomo, O. T. “Common Solution Of Split Equilibrium Problem And Fixed Point Problem With No Prior Knowledge Of Operator Norm”, *UPB Sci. Bull., Series A*, 80(1), 175-190 (2018).
- [16] Zhang, Y., and Gui, Y. “.Strong Convergence Theorem For Split Equilibrium Problem And Fixed Point Problem In Hilbert Spaces”, *Int. Math*, 12(9), 413-427 (2017).
- [17] Cho, Y. J., Qin, X., And Im Kang. J. “Convergence Theorems Based On Hybrid Methods For Generalized Equilibrium Problems And Fixed Point Problems. *Nonlinear Analysis: Theory, Methods And Applications*”, 71(9), 4203-4214 (2009).

- [18] Gibali, A., Reich, S., and Zalas, R. “Outer Approximation Methods For Solving Variational Inequalities In Hilbert Space. *Optimization*”, 66(3), 417-437 (2017).
- [19] Cegielski, A., Gibali, A., Reich, S., and Zalas, R. “Outer Approximation Methods For Solving Variational Inequalities Defined Over The Solution Set Of a Split Convex Feasibility Problem. *Numerical Functional Analysis And Optimization*”, 41(9), 1089-1108 (2017).
- [20] Iiduka, H. “Fixed Point Optimization Algorithm And Its Application To network bandwidth allocation”, *Journal Of Computational And Applied Mathematics*, 236(7), 1733-1742 (2012).
- [21] Alakoya, T. O., Jolaoso, L. O., Taiwo, A., And Mewomo, O. T. “Inertial Algorithm With Self-Adaptive Step Size For Split Common Null Point And Common Fixed Point Problems For Multivalued Mappings In Banach Spaces”, *Optimization*, 1-35 (2021).
- [22] Kazmi, K. R., and Rizvi, S. H. “Iterative Approximation Of a Common Solution Of a Split Equilibrium Problem, a Variational Inequality Problem And a Fixed Point Problem”, *Journal Of The Egyptian Mathematical Society*, 21(1), 44-51 (2013).
- [23] Blum, Eugen. “From Optimization And Variational Inequalities To Equilibrium Problems”, *Math. student* 63: 123-145 (1994).